

1 **Global analysis of building façade exposure to water penetration in Chile**

2 José M. Pérez-Bella^a, Javier Domínguez-Hernández^{a,*}, Enrique Cano-Suñén^a, Juan J. del Coz-Díaz^b, Mar
3 Alonso-Martínez^b

4 ^a *Department of Construction Engineering, Engineering and Architecture School, University of Zaragoza,*
5 *María de Luna, s/n, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain.*

6 ^b *Department of Construction Engineering, University of Oviedo, Edificio Departamental Viesques nº 7,*
7 *33204 Gijón, Spain.*

8

9 **Abstract**

10 In this study, the exposure of building façades in Chile to wind-driven rain and driving rain wind pressure
11 was analysed. Daily climatic data from 29 weather stations throughout Chile were used to determine these
12 exposures in scalar terms and are presented in exposure maps. These values were used to estimate the risk
13 index for water penetration at each location and to determine the relationships between the different
14 exposure indices calculated from the daily, monthly, and annual data. Finally, the directional
15 characterisations of these exposures were determined with an alternative method that was based on
16 climatic data from the Chilean stations. This method was used to quantify the exposure of façades
17 oriented in any direction in 6 cities that represent the country's climate: Santiago, Concepción, La Serena,
18 Temuco, Antofagasta, and Puerto Montt. In general, the exposure of façades to water penetration
19 progressively increases from north to south. However, this pattern is affected by the topography of each
20 location, especially in the capital and southern regions. Valdivia, which is located in the centre, and
21 Balmaceda, which is located in the south, showed the greatest risk of water penetration in Chilean
22 façades.

23 **Keywords**

24 Wind-driven rain; Wind pressure; Water tightness; Risk assessment; Building design; Chile

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* Corresponding author. Department of Construction Engineering, University of Zaragoza, María de Luna, s/n, 50018, Zaragoza, Spain. Tel.Fax: +34 976 76 21 00.
E-mail address: javdom@unizar.es (Javier Domínguez-Hernández)

1

2 **1. Introduction**

3 Wind during atmospheric precipitation adds a horizontal component to the velocity of each raindrop,
4 which may affect vertical surfaces such as building façades [1]. This phenomenon (wind-driven rain or
5 WDR) is the primary cause of liquid water build-up on building enclosures. Moreover, when combined
6 with the concurrent wind pressure that is exerted on the façade (driving rain wind pressure or DRWP),
7 increases the risk of humidity penetration into the building [2-4].

8 In addition, the penetration of atmospheric water into façade materials alters the habitability of the
9 building and affects occupant health [5, 6]. This penetration reduces the thermal insulation provided by
10 these materials [7, 8] and has a number of adverse effects (e.g., corrosion, chemical attack, frost damage,
11 salt transport, efflorescence, discoloration, soiling, loss of adherence, biological growth, deformation,
12 cracking, etc.) that increase the maintenance costs for the building [9-14].

13 To design building enclosures that prevent or limit the penetration of atmospheric water, the exposure of
14 façades to driving rain and simultaneous wind pressure must be characterised at each location [15]. Thus,
15 multiple researchers have attempted to determine the WDR and DRWP in different locations and
16 countries [16-23]. However, only a few researchers have conducted directional studies for both exposures
17 to determine the exposures of all façade orientations at multiples locations.

18 The objective of this study was to determine the WDR and DRWP in scalar terms for various locations in
19 Chile subjected to different climates, from the northern desert regions (e.g., Atacama desert) to the
20 southern subantarctic zones (e.g., the archipelago of Tierra del Fuego). The overall exposure of these
21 façades to water penetration was characterised by combining both scalar exposures into a single
22 integrated index (Risk Index of Water Penetration or RIWP) [24].

1 This scalar characterisation was complemented by a directional distribution analysis of both exposures
2 relative to various building façade orientations. A new calculation method that uses climatic data, which
3 are normally recorded by weather stations in Chile, is suggested in this study. This method was applied to
4 6 cities distributed throughout Chile that represent the country's diverse climatic conditions.

5 Overall, this study establishes a complete characterisation method (both scalar and directional) for the
6 climatic exposures that are most relevant for water penetration in building façades in Chile. This
7 characterisation can be used with the indicators and maps presented to improve building design by
8 establishing normative requirements adjusted for the exposure characteristics of each location.

9 **2. Background**

10 Atmospheric water that hits the facades due to WDR and the concurrent DRWP are the main causes of
11 unwanted humidity penetration into buildings [25]. Thus, all tests used to determine the maximum water
12 tightness of a façade system must recreate extreme conditions that represent both exposure parameters
13 [26-28].

14 Regarding the primary cause of humidity penetration into façades without significant pores or fissures (<1
15 mm), various studies have indicated that the presence of water is less important than the concurrent wind
16 pressure [3]. Therefore, water tightness tests that are usually applied to new and relatively flawless
17 enclosures use pressure difference as the main test parameter. However, in deteriorated façades (i.e., those
18 with defects or fissures >5 mm), the presence of water becomes the main parameter because it can
19 penetrate the enclosure even in the absence of significant wind pressure [29].

20 Due to the variety of materials, finishes and conservation or maintenance states of the façades, neither of
21 these parameters can be ignored when characterising the global risk of water penetration. Thus,
22 determining the WDR and DRWP façade exposure conditions in each location is a required preliminary
23 step for optimising their design.

1 Several researchers have used semi-empirical methods to characterise WDR exposure, which enabled
 2 them to obtain approximate results from the recorded climatic data at each location [30, 31]. The general
 3 formulation of these methods (called the “WDR relationship”) allows for assessing the WDR_{θ} (mm) that
 4 hits a façade of orientation θ (°) by using wind direction D (°), wind velocity U (m/s) and rain R_h (mm)
 5 records from each location (Eq. 1). This relationship is fit by using an empirical coefficient k that varies
 6 with precipitation type and is usually between 0.2 and 0.25 s/m [32, 33].

$$WDR_{\theta} = k \cdot U \cdot R_h \cdot \cos(D - \theta) \quad (1)$$

7 This relationship was recently standardised in ISO 15927-3:2009 [34], setting the coefficient k to $2/9$ s/m
 8 and using an exponential fit (see Eq. 2). In addition, hourly wind and precipitation data, which were
 9 simultaneously recorded over N years, were used (a historic series of more than 10 years was preferred) as
 10 a reference for calculating the yearly average wind-driven rain $WDR_{A\theta}$ (mm). Moreover, the wind velocity
 11 U_{10} (m/s) must be recorded under standardised conditions at a height of 10 m on clear terrain without
 12 obstacles [35].

$$WDR_{A\theta} = \frac{2}{9} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m U_{10i} \cdot (R_{hi})^{\frac{8}{9}} \cdot \cos(D_i - \theta)}{N} \quad (2)$$

13 To quantify the amount of water hitting a façade orientation θ , only the m intervals during which the wind
 14 direction D drives the precipitation over the façade’s surface must be considered in the summation (see
 15 Fig. 1) [36].

16

17 **Fig. 1.** Cosine projection method for the semi-empirical calculation of wind-driven rain over a particular
 18 façade with an orientation θ [36].

19

1 However, this standard is rarely used because many countries do not have hourly climatic data for
2 multiple locations that were collected over a period of more than 10 years. Moreover, the absence of
3 simultaneous wind direction records usually prevents the generalisation of these directional calculations
4 and restricts them to specific stations [37]. Thus, in recent years, various studies have attempted to obtain
5 directional results that are comparable to those of the ISO standard, which is based on more frequently
6 collected climatic data (e.g., synoptic data recorded 6 or 8 times a day) [38, 39].

7 All of these limitations have forced studies that are aimed at characterising exposure over vast areas to
8 use formulations based on the available climatic data from more weather stations. Thus, the annual
9 Driving Rain Index (*aDRI*) is the most commonly WDR exposure measure in many countries [1, 19-23].

10 This index, which is a simplification of the WDR relationship, ignores the empirical fitting coefficient k
11 and determines the annual exposure *aDRI* (m^2/s) as the product of m precipitation records R_h (mm) and
12 wind velocities U_{10} (m/s) obtained over a period of N years at each location (see Eq. 3). Generally, the
13 directional component is disregarded. Consequently, the obtained characterisation is scalar and does not
14 account for the differences between the specific exposures of every possible enclosure orientation [40].

$$aDRI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m U_{10i} \cdot \left(\frac{R_{hi}}{1000} \right)}{N} \quad (3)$$

15 The annual average rain and wind velocity (*aaDRI*), the monthly average (*maDRI*), or the daily average
16 (*daDRI*) data can be used to calculate this index. Because the average-related error and the error of the
17 simultaneity between the wind and rain recordings are lower, the greater the data recording frequency is,
18 the more precise are the indices [41, 42].

19 Due to their simplicity, these indices are efficient tools for comparing the WDR exposure of different
20 locations with limited climatic data. Although this index does not quantify the WDR that affects the

1 façades, some studies have been conducted to establish empirical fitting coefficients that relate the
 2 obtained *aDRI* values (m²/s) to the quantity of WDR that is received by the building enclosure [43].
 3 Moreover, Bernoulli's equation can be used to characterise the exposure of a façade with an orientation θ
 4 (°) to wind pressure $DRWP_{\theta}$ (Pa) concurrent with WDR [3], where U (m/s) and D (°) represent the
 5 velocity and direction records, respectively, for the winds that occur with significant precipitation (>0.05
 6 mm). For this calculation, a pressure coefficient C_p of 1 and an air density ρ_{air} of 1.2 kg/m³ (Eq. 4) can be
 7 used in the absence of more accurate data.

$$DRWP_{\theta} = C_p \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_{air} \cdot U^2 \cdot \cos(D - \theta) \quad (4)$$

8 To determine the average DRWP exposure, the average of the m $DRWP_{\theta}$ exposures over the number of
 9 years being considered can be used (Eq. 5). Only records where the wind direction D creates a positive
 10 wind pressure over the surface of the enclosure should be considered in the summation (see Fig. 1).
 11 Furthermore, the wind velocity value U_{10} (m/s) should be obtained by using the same standardised
 12 recording conditions that are established for Equations 2 and 3 (a height of 10 m on a clear terrain with no
 13 obstacles).

$$DRWP_{A\theta} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_{air\ i} \cdot U_{10i}^2 \cdot \cos(D_i - \theta)}{m} \quad (5)$$

14 As for *aDRI*, the use of more frequent wind records results in more accurate DRWP exposure estimates
 15 by precisely identifying the direction D associated with the velocity data U_{10} and by dismissing wind
 16 records that do not occur with significant precipitation.

17 Similar to WDR exposure, the wind pressure during WDR can be characterised by scalar terms when
 18 wind direction data are unavailable. In this case, the directional component must be eliminated from the

1 general expression, and all m records that occur simultaneously with rain must be considered in the
2 summation (Eq. 6).

$$DRWP_A = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_{air\ i} \cdot U_{10i}^2}{m} \quad (6)$$

3 The previous equations (Eq. 3 and 6) may be used to evaluate the risk of water penetration on the
4 enclosures by characterising the two climatic parameters that are most relevant to such penetration in the
5 same location (i.e., WDR and DRWP). The scalar or directional nature of this characterisation and its
6 accuracy will only depend on the quality of the available climatic records from the various weather
7 stations selected for the analysis.

8 In Section 3.2 of this work, the exposures of 29 Chilean cities are analysed in scalar terms using daily
9 climatic data for each location collected over 10 years. This scalar analysis is completed in Section 3.3 by
10 calculating the RIWP [24] and by establishing a single, qualitative classification for the water penetration
11 risk on the façades in the different studied locations. In addition, the relationships between the scalar
12 indices (*aaDRI*, *maDRI*, and *daDRI*) are examined and compared to those of other countries.

13 Section 4 concludes by suggesting a new alternative method of characterisation for the directional
14 distribution of the WDR and DRWP exposures. For this purpose, the proposed method only uses daily
15 precipitation data and wind frequency and intensity reports for a limited number of directions. This
16 method has been used to determine both directional exposures for 6 major Chilean cities.

17

18 **3. The scalar characterisation of WDR and DRWP in Chile**

19 *3.1 The Chilean perspective*

1 Analysing previous exposures in Chile is interesting because geographic and atmospheric conditions vary
2 widely throughout this territory. The large coast running along the country (from a latitude of 18°S to
3 55°S, excluding the Antarctic territory) covers over 4,000 km and encompasses diverse climatic regions
4 with different patterns of humidity exposure on the façades.

5 The Andes cause significant changes in altitude in the eastern part of the country and reach heights of up
6 to 6,000 meters in some locations that are less than 200 km from the coast (Ojos del Salado volcano).
7 This mountain range also isolates the country from the humid air masses of the continent (rain shadow
8 phenomenon) and increases the influence of the South-Eastern Pacific subtropical anticyclone, Humboldt
9 Current, and Hadley cell on the country's climate (Fig. 2).

10 This subtropical anticyclone is perennially located between 30°S and 80°W and induces stable, high-
11 pressures conditions that prevent precipitation fronts in the northern region of Chile [44]. However, air
12 currents generated by the anticyclone from the south transport oceanic humidity and can generate mist in
13 this region. The Humboldt Current accentuates the lack of precipitation on the North Coast by dragging
14 cold water to the oceanic surface, which reduces superficial evaporation and convective cloud formation
15 [45]. These effects are enhanced by the Hadley cell, which transports dry air from the atmospheric layers
16 [46]. Consequently, the northern part of the country (latitudes 18°S to 30°S) has a very arid climate with
17 precipitation of less than 1 mm/year (e.g., Arica, Iquique and Atacama desert airports).

18 Low-pressure systems can move to the southern coast, which is far from these influences, and cause
19 predominately west-east winds that transport oceanic humidity and favour precipitation. Thus, the
20 southern climate of the country is rainy with prolonged wet seasons (the precipitation rates are greater
21 than 1,500 mm/year south of a latitude of 42°S and it is impossible to define a dry summer). In addition,
22 the low temperatures from the advanced latitudes further south progressively increase snow precipitation.

1 The centre of the country has a transitional climate that is conditioned by topographic height, with
2 progressively more abundant precipitation from north to south. Consequently, several main climate
3 subtypes exist in Chile, including desert, Mediterranean, continental, and oceanic climates [47].

4

5 **Fig. 2.** Locations of the weather stations used in this study and the most relevant geographic/atmospheric
6 factors that impact the Chilean climate.

7

8 *3.2 WDR and DRWP analysis*

9 Since 1884, the Meteorological Directorate of Chile (DMC) has been charged with providing
10 meteorological services to the country. Currently, the DMC possesses historic climate data collected from
11 various locations [48]. In this study, 29 weather stations located in the continental part of the country and
12 the Juan Fernández Islands were selected (Table 1). Most of these stations are located in airports and
13 aerodromes near urban centres. Thus, their climatic conditions can be considered similar to those of
14 neighbouring cities.

15

16 **Table 1.** Summary of the analysed Chilean weather stations.

17

18 All of the stations have climatic data records for precipitation and wind. These data were collected for at
19 least 10 years (November 2002 - October 2012). The precipitation data corresponded to 4 daily recordings
20 (at 6-hour intervals), from which the total daily rainfall can be calculated. Regarding wind velocity and
21 direction, daily reports of frequency and intensity are available based on a variable number of recordings

1 (8 to 24 daily observations, depending on the station). These reports contain the number of daily
2 observations where the wind direction can be associated with one of the 8 main geographic orientations
3 (frequency F). In addition, these reports contain the average velocity associated with each direction
4 (intensity I) (see Table 2). The “Variable” direction (Vrb) encompasses records in which a specific wind
5 direction cannot be assigned. In contrast, the “Calm” designation encompasses records in which the wind
6 velocity was negligible.

7

8 **Table 2.** Example of ten daily reports for wind velocity and direction (*data: Jan. 2011, Santiago-Quinta*
9 *Normal*).

10

11 With these meteorological records, the WDR and DRWP exposures for the various locations analysed
12 could be characterised in scalar terms by using Equations 3 and 6. Thus, the $daDRI$ (m^2/s), $maDRI$ (m^2/s),
13 and $aaDRI$ (m^2/s) indices were used to determine the scalar exposure to WDR for each location based on
14 the average daily, monthly and annual precipitation R_h (mm) and wind velocity U_{10} (m/s) data,
15 respectively (see Eq. 3).

16 The daily precipitation for each location can be obtained by adding the 4 daily observations for each
17 station. From the total daily values, the total monthly or yearly values can be calculated for the $N=10$
18 year historical series.

19 To obtain the daily average wind velocity values from the frequency and intensity reports that were
20 available from the Chilean stations, the intensity records for each of the $D=8$ main geographic
21 orientations were averaged for each day i (Eq. 7). In addition, “Variable” direction measurements were
22 also incorporated to accurately estimate the average value.

$$U_{10i} = \frac{F_{Vrb\ i} \cdot I_{Vrb\ i} + \sum_{D=1}^8 F_{D\ i} \cdot I_{D\ i}}{Total\ records_i} \quad (7)$$

1 The monthly and annual wind velocity averages were calculated from the daily averages for each
 2 location. These averages were used to determine the *maDRI* and *aaDRI* indices. Fig. 3 geographically
 3 represents the WDR exposure characterisation based on the *daDRI* value. This index is presented with the
 4 *maDRI* and *aaDRI* values in Table 3.

5

6 **Fig. 3.** WDR exposure map of Chile.

7

8 A constant air density value ρ_{air} of 1.2 kg/m^3 was used in the scalar $DRWP_A$ (Pa) calculation (see Eq. 6)
 9 and the average wind velocities were obtained from Eq. 7. Only the *m* average wind velocity values,
 10 which correspond to days with significant precipitation ($>0.05\text{ mm}$), were considered for this calculation.
 11 The $DRWP_A$ values obtained by following this method are shown in Fig. 4 and are detailed in Table 3.

12

13 **Fig. 4.** DRWP exposure map of Chile.

14

15 **Table 3.** Scalar characterisation of WDR and DRWP exposure for 29 Chilean cities (*data: November*
 16 *2002- October 2012*).

17

18 *3.3 Risk Index of Water Penetration*

1 Once the WDR and DRWP exposure values were calculated, they can be combined to create a single
 2 index that includes the severity of both parameters that are most relevant for the water penetration
 3 process. This risk index of water penetration (or *RIWP*) can be used to compare the combined exposure
 4 from various locations by characterising the overall water penetration risk [24]. For this purpose, each
 5 exposure parameter associated with a location *j* is normalised with respect to the maximum and minimum
 6 values identified from the available sample base (Eq. 8 and 9).

$$daDRI_{normalised\ j} = \frac{daDRI_j - daDRI_{min}}{daDRI_{max} - daDRI_{min}} \quad (8)$$

$$DRWP_{A\ normalised\ j} = \frac{DRWP_{Aj} - DRWP_{Amin}}{DRWP_{Amax} - DRWP_{Amin}} \quad (9)$$

7 Both normalised values (oscillating between 0 and 1) were combined in Eq. 10 to obtain the *RIWP* for
 8 each location. Thus, greater normalised values correspond to increased risk of water penetration at the
 9 location. Both exposures were assumed to influence the penetration process equally. Therefore, the
 10 obtained index can be used for façades with different surface finishes, where the influence of one
 11 exposure may oscillate relative to the influence of another [3].

$$RIWP_j = \sqrt{(daDRI_{normalised\ j})^2 + (DRWP_{A\ normalised\ j})^2} \quad (10)$$

12 The results for the 29 considered locations are presented in Table 3. This calculation identified the
 13 locations with similar risks of water penetration and established quantitative limits that can be used to
 14 determine the best-adapted façade design for each risk level. Based on previously suggested limits [24],
 15 Fig. 5 indicates the Chilean locations with moderate ($0.4 \leq RIWP < 0.7$), high ($0.7 \leq RIWP < 1.0$), or
 16 severe ($RIWP \geq 1.0$) risks.

17

1 **Fig. 5.** Classification of locations with greater risk of water penetration in Chile. *Only sites with radii (i.e.*
2 *RIWP values) that are at risk of water penetration greater than 0.4 were named.*

3

4 *3.4 Scalar results and discussion*

5 As expected, the WDR exposure in the considered locations significantly varied from negligible in the
6 north (Iquique, 0.0002 m²/s) to greater than 8 m²/s in Valdivia (centre of the country). However, these
7 values are within the characteristic range of other countries, such as Greece, Nigeria, Spain, and Turkey
8 [20-23], and below the characteristic range of humid countries, such as India or Ireland [19, 49].

9 In general, the *daDRI* value progressively increased from the north to Puerto Montt and decreased again
10 further south. The conditions at Santiago (with indices of less than 0.6 m²/s) must be highlighted because
11 this area is highly protected by calm winds that dominate the area during the winter months (when the
12 majority of precipitation occurs). Further south, Chile Chico can also be considered as a protected
13 location. Here, the rain shadow caused by the nearby mountains that separate this location from the
14 Pacific Ocean, significantly reduces its average annual precipitation and exposure to WDR.

15 When comparing the WDR exposure indices calculated from either average daily or monthly data, fitting
16 can be used to estimate the *daDRI* value from the monthly average wind velocity and precipitation (Fig.
17 6). A similar fit can be determined to estimate the *daDRI* value from annual average data (Fig. 7). Both
18 expressions can be useful when accurately estimating the WDR exposure in Chilean locations where the
19 availability of weather data is limited.

20

21 **Fig. 6.** Best fit-linear relationship between *daDRI* and *maDRI*.

22

1 **Fig. 7.** Best fit-linear relationship between *daDRI* and *aaDRI*.

2

3 The existing relationship between the *maDRI* and *aaDRI* was analysed for the 29 locations (Fig. 8). This
4 relationship is similar to those observed in other countries (e.g., Greece, Nigeria, and Spain), which
5 suggested that it could be extrapolated to other regions. In addition, this situation differs from the
6 situation in other countries where greater precipitation rates and seasonal atmospheric phenomena (e.g.,
7 India) may cause significant error.

8

9 **Fig. 8.** Best fit-linear relationship between *maDRI* and *aaDRI*, and a comparison between different
10 countries.

11

12 Moreover, the DRWP exposure values fluctuate from 0.57 Pa in Santiago to 34.67 Pa in Balmaceda.
13 There is no clear distribution pattern that characterises these exposures because high $DRWP_A$ values can
14 be observed in the north (Calama, 26.81 Pa) and South (Balmaceda; Punta Arenas, 29.61 Pa; Puerto
15 Williams, 23.38 Pa; Chile Chico, 17.93 Pa). The lowest DRWP exposure values in Chile were found in
16 and near Santiago due to the calm winds that characterise the rainy season.

17 To characterise this exposure using climatic records collected in any location of Chile, Fig. 9 depicts the
18 relationship between the average wind pressure and the previously calculated $DRWP_A$ values at each
19 location. The average wind pressure was calculated by using an air density of 1.2 kg/m^3 and the average
20 wind velocity for each day of the studied period, regardless of precipitation. This mathematical fit
21 includes an acceptable coefficient of determination R^2 and indicates how the wind pressure during rainfall

1 in the considered locations is generally less in Chile than the average wind pressure (represented by the
2 dots below the broken line in Fig. 9).

3

4 **Fig. 9.** Best fit-linear relationship between $DRWP_A$ and *mean wind pressure*.

5

6 Furthermore, the *RIWP* indicates that 55% of the analysed locations (16 out of 29) can be regarded as a
7 low risk for water penetration ($RIWP < 0.4$). However, more than 80% of locations are regarded as low risk
8 in other countries, such as Spain [24]. In addition, the high risk value identified in Valdivia is mainly due
9 to the large volume of WDR received by the façades. However, the similar risk value for Balmaceda is
10 due to the high wind pressure that coincided with precipitation.

11 Thus, two groups of locations are distinguishable in Figure 5. First, Balmaceda, Punta Arenas, Puerto
12 Williams and Chile Chico have significant risk levels due to their high wind pressure, which facilitates
13 water penetration into buildings despite the small volume of WDR. Calama is peculiar due to its low
14 annual precipitation and WDR (5.7 mm/year; $daDRI$ 0.023 m²/s), which makes the penetration of
15 enclosures by water unlikely (despite the high $DRWP$ exposure). In contrast, Valdivia, Puerto Montt,
16 Osorno, Chillán and Temuco have a significantly greater risk of water penetration mainly due to the
17 WDR rather than the concurrent wind pressure.

18 As expected, the risk of water penetration in Santiago is abnormally low considering its annual
19 precipitation rate and geographic position in the centre of the country (Santiago, 0.03; Tobalaba, 0.05;
20 Pudahuel, 0.11). The trajectory of precipitation in this city, which is normally vertical due to the absence
21 of simultaneous wind, protects the vertical enclosures from atmospheric rain. This protection results in
22 negligible water penetration risk on the façades.

1 The above scalar results provide a useful estimate of the mean exposure conditions in the country using
2 the climatic data available. However, the driving rain indices calculated do not provide the quantity of
3 WDR (l/m^2) and the exposure values should be adjusted for façades without standardised conditions (at a
4 height of 10 m on clear terrain without obstacles).

5 Moreover, the time interval of exposure is also an important factor to be considered. Usually, the water
6 penetration into building façades does not develop throughout a complete year but intensifies during short
7 time intervals [34]. Thus, the peak values of wind velocity and precipitation associated with wetting
8 stages could be more important than mean values and should also be considered for a future
9 comprehensive characterisation of the exposure in the country.

10

11 **4. Directional characterisation of WDR and DRWP in Chile**

12 The simultaneous occurrence of WDR and DRWP over the various façades of a building can vary greatly
13 in its orientation and normal rain and wind conditions. Thus, it is important to quantify the directional
14 distribution of exposure to optimise façade designs for different locations.

15 The precipitation records and wind frequency and intensity reports that are available from the Chilean
16 stations do not include hourly data and cannot be directly used in the directional calculations of ISO
17 15927-3:2009 (see Eq. 2). However, these data can be used to estimate the directional distribution of both
18 exposures with a new calculation process, which is explained below. This method was used to estimate
19 the directional distribution of WDR and DRWP exposures in 6 major Chilean cities throughout the
20 country (Antofagasta, La Serena, Santiago, Concepción, Temuco and Puerto Montt).

21 Before performing a directional characterisation of the WDR exposure in the studied locations, the total
22 daily precipitation R_h (mm) must be proportionally distributed among the directions analysed by the

1 weather stations, including the “variable” and “calm” directions (Eq. 11). For this purpose, the daily wind
 2 frequency distribution F_D for each direction and the total records for each day i were used (see Table 2).

$$R_{hi D} = R_{hi} \cdot \frac{F_{D i}}{\text{Total records}_i} \quad (11)$$

3 Once known, the daily precipitation distribution $R_{h D}$ (mm) and the average daily wind intensity I_D (m/s)
 4 for each direction can be used to determine the directional component $daDRI_D$ (m^2/s) for each of the main
 5 $D=8$ orientations (Eq. 12). This equation considers the m daily precipitation records collected throughout
 6 the considered N years (November 2002-October 2012).

$$daDRI_D = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m \left[I_{D i} \cdot \left(\frac{R_{hi D}}{1000} \right) + I_{Vrb i} \cdot \left(\frac{R_{hi Vrb}}{1000} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{F_{D i}}{\text{Total records}_i - F_{Vrb i} - F_{calm i}} \right) \right]}{N} \quad (12)$$

7 It is assumed that rain in the “calm” direction does not increase WDR on the façades. Moreover, the
 8 contribution of WDR from the “variable” direction was proportionally distributed among the 8 main
 9 orientations based on the number of records F_D associated with each direction. The number of records
 10 with “variable” direction can be used for this calculation and oscillated from 0.9% in Santiago to 23% in
 11 Temuco for the 6 locations discussed in this section.

12 Fig. 10 shows the component $daDRI_D$ that is associated with each of the main geographic orientations for
 13 the 6 analysed cities. As expected, the sum of the 8 directional components yields the previously
 14 calculated scalar $daDRI$ value for each location.

15

16 **Fig. 10.** Directional component of the $daDRI$ value for the 8 main geographical directions (m^2/s) in six
 17 major cities in Chile.

18

1 The directional decomposition of the scalar $daDRI$ into its main orientations can be used to estimate the
 2 average annual WDR for any possible enclosure orientation. For this estimation, Eq. 13 was based on the
 3 same cosine projection method used in ISO 15927-3:2009 (see Figure 1). The only elements required for
 4 this calculation are the directional components $daDRI_D$, which are associated with a direction D ($^\circ$) that
 5 increases the WDR over a façade at orientation θ (i.e., between $\theta \pm 90^\circ$). For example, to calculate the
 6 index of exposure over a façade with a 60° north orientation ($daDRI_{60^\circ}$), the summation must include the
 7 following components: $daDRI_N$, $daDRI_{NE}$, $daDRI_E$, and $daDRI_{SE}$.

$$daDRI_\theta = \sum daDRI_D \cdot \cos(D - \theta) \quad (13)$$

8 Fig. 11 shows the calculated directional characterisation of the WDR exposures for each of the previously
 9 considered cities for façades with orientations of θ at 15° intervals. In addition, this calculation can be
 10 extrapolated to any weather station with wind frequency and intensity reports for a limited number of
 11 directions.

12
 13 **Fig. 11.** Directional $daDRI$ values (m^2/s) for 6 major cities in Chile (*angles are measured in degrees from*
 14 *the north*).

15
 16 A similar process was followed to use data recorded by Chilean weather stations to estimate the
 17 directional distribution of the DRWP exposure. Thus, the average daily wind velocity $U_{10\theta}$ (m/s)
 18 perpendicular to a specified orientation θ ($^\circ$) was estimated from the intensity I_D (m/s) and frequency F_D
 19 records gathered during the day from the analysed directions, including the “variable” direction (Eq. 14).

20 Both summations only need to consider records in which the direction D may induce a positive wind
 21 pressure on the orientation under analysis (i.e., those within the interval $\theta \pm 90^\circ$). Again, wind records

1 associated with the “variable” direction were proportionally distributed among the 8 main geographic
 2 orientations because it was impossible to assign them to a specific direction.

$$U_{10i\theta} = \frac{\sum \left(F_{Di} \cdot I_{Di} + F_{Vrb i} \cdot I_{Vrb i} \cdot \frac{F_{Di}}{Total\ records_i - F_{Vrb i} - F_{calm i}} \right) \cdot \cos(D - \theta)}{\sum \left(F_{Di} + F_{Vrb i} \cdot \frac{F_{Di}}{Total\ records_i - F_{Vrb i} - F_{calm i}} \right)} \quad (14)$$

3 Once the average wind velocity perpendicular to an orientation θ is known for each day i , the average
 4 exposure $DRWP_{A\theta}$ (Pa) can be calculated from Eq. 15 by using a constant air density ρ_{air} of 1.2 kg/m^3 and
 5 by considering all m daily velocities $U_{10\theta}$ occurred on days with significant precipitation ($>0.05\text{ mm}$).

6 Fig. 12 shows the results for façade orientations with 15° intervals in the 6 cities.

$$DRWP_{A\theta} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho_{air} \cdot \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (U_{10i\theta})^2}{m} \quad (15)$$

7

8 **Fig. 12.** Directional $DRWP_A$ values (Pa) for 6 major cities in Chile (*angles are measured in degrees from*
 9 *the north*).

10

11 4.1 Directional results and discussion

12 Figs. 11 and 12 indicate that both exposures have a similar directional distribution in the studied
 13 locations. The main WDR exposures in Antofagasta and Santiago are oriented to the south. The greatest
 14 values in Concepción, Temuco, and Puerto Montt were obtained for orientations that were approximately
 15 northward. In La Serena, the greatest WDR exposure occurred for the east and west orientations.

1 Similarly, the maximum DRWP value for Antofagasta was for southern orientations, while the maximum
2 DRWP values for Concepcion, Temuco and Puerto Montt were for north-northeast orientations. However,
3 in La Serena, the greatest WDR exposure was achieved along the western orientation. In this city, the
4 most intense precipitation occurs simultaneously with eastern winds, which increase the *daDRI* in this
5 direction. In contrast, the strongest winds that occurred simultaneously with rain came from the west.

6 An analogous situation occurred in Santiago, where the WDR exposure was much greater for the façades
7 with a southern orientation, despite the similar DRWP exposures of the northern and southern orientations
8 (Table 4). The north-south orientations of the main exposures in the capital were consistent with the
9 topographic conditions of its surrounding terrain. The city is flanked by two mountain ranges to the east
10 and west, which protect it from east and west winds.

11 This method provides a new alternative for estimating mean directional exposures in countries where the
12 available climatic data are incompatible with ISO 15927-3:2009. In this case, only daily precipitation
13 records and wind frequency-intensity reports for a limited number of directions are needed. However, as
14 for the scalar analysis, peak values of wind velocity and precipitation associated with wetting stages
15 should also be considered for a complete characterisation of the directional exposure. Moreover, the
16 proposed method can lead to some uncertainty in locations with a large number of "variable" direction
17 records, due to the proportional distribution applied in Eqs. 12 and 14.

18

19 **Table 4.** Comparison of the scalar indices and maximum directional values for the WDR and DRWP
20 exposures.

21

1 Finally, the scalar exposure values that were initially obtained for each location were related to the
2 maximum directional value identified for a façade orientation. As shown in Fig. 13, the maximum
3 directional exposure for the 6 locations can be estimated by using the scalar exposure results.

4

5 **Fig. 13.** Best fit-linear relationships between the scalar and maximum directional values for the WDR and
6 DRWP exposures.

7

8 The high coefficients of determination for both fits suggest that these expressions could be used to
9 estimate the maximum directional exposure in the analysed Chilean locations with only limited climatic
10 data or in the absence of wind direction data. These relationships could be used to assign homogeneous
11 designs for all building façades by using the maximum predicted directional value for the location.

12

13 **5. Conclusions**

14 This study presents a global analysis of building exposure to WDR and DRWP in Chile. Scalar WDR and
15 DRWP exposure values were determined for various locations throughout the country and characterised
16 under different climatic conditions. These results were used to identify several mathematical relationships
17 for estimating exposure values based on available climatic records from all weather stations. In addition,
18 combining both exposures into a risk index of water penetration has been used to assess the overall risk
19 for each location. Furthermore, various exposure and risk maps have been created to improve the design
20 of Chilean façades by adapting them to the operating conditions that are predicted for each location.

21 Design optimisation also requires identifying the directional distribution of the WDR and DRWP
22 exposures. Thus, a new calculation process is required that uses climatic data from Chilean weather

1 stations. This method was used to estimate the directional exposure in 6 major Chilean cities. In addition,
2 the suggested calculation process is potentially an alternative for countries and regions where available
3 climatic data do not comply with the ISO 15927-3:2009 requirements. The directional results suggest that
4 it is possible to estimate the maximum directional exposure with only the characteristic scalar exposure
5 for each location. This method could be useful for assigning a homogeneous design for all façades based
6 on the maximum estimated directional value, even in locations of Chile with no directional weather
7 records.

8

9 **Acknowledgments**

10 These results were obtained from data provided by the Meteorological Directorate of Chile, General
11 Directorate of Civil Aviation (DCM). This work was partial financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science
12 and Innovation co-financed with FEDER funds under the Research Project BIA2012-31609. We also
13 recognise Javier Jiménez Sevillano for his help in the data collection and processing.

14

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Table 1.
Summary of the analysed Chilean weather stations.

WEATHER STATION	ALT. (m)	LATITUDE (DD)	LONGITUDE (DD)	Mean rainfall (mm)
Arica airport	63	-18.3514 ^o	-70.3358 ^o	0.5
Iquique airport	52	-20.5467 ^o	-70.1772 ^o	0.6
Calama aerodrome	2293	-22.4953 ^o	-69.9044 ^o	5.7
Antofagasta (<i>Cerro Moreno airport</i>)	113	-23.4503 ^o	-70.4411 ^o	1.7
Atacama desert airport	204	-27.2639 ^o	-70.7742 ^o	0.1
La Serena (<i>La Florida aerodrome</i>)	142	-29.9172 ^o	-71.2003 ^o	78.5
Valparaiso aerodrome	330	-33.0367 ^o	-71.5342 ^o	372.5
Santo Domingo aerodrome	75	-33.6550 ^o	-71.6142 ^o	325.0
Santiago (<i>Quinta Normal</i>)	527	-33.4450 ^o	-70.6828 ^o	312.5
Tobalaba aerodrome	650	-33.4544 ^o	-70.5478 ^o	347.2
Pudahuel Santiago	480	-33.5419 ^o	-70.7944 ^o	261.6
Juan Fernández	35	-33.6367 ^o	-78.8350 ^o	1041.5
Curico aerodrome	225	-34.9664 ^o	-71.2167 ^o	701.9
Chillán aerodrome	151	-36.5872 ^o	-72.0400 ^o	1107.0
Concepción (<i>Carriel Sur airport</i>)	12	-36.7792 ^o	-73.0622 ^o	110.1
Los Ángeles aerodrome	120	-37.4028 ^o	-72.4200 ^o	1074.4
Temuco (<i>Maqueue aerodrome</i>)	92	-38.7700 ^o	-72.6369 ^o	1157.4
Valdivia aerodrome	18	-39.6511 ^o	-73.0817 ^o	1871.0
Osorno aerodrome	61	-40.6050 ^o	-73.0608 ^o	1331.8
Puerto Montt (<i>El Tepual airport</i>)	85	-41.4350 ^o	-73.0975 ^o	1802.5
Futaleufu aerodrome	350	-43.1892 ^o	-71.8492 ^o	2081.0
Alto Palena aerodrome	281	-43.6117 ^o	-71.8053 ^o	1622.3
Puerto Aysén aerodrome	11	-45.3961 ^o	-72.6639 ^o	2313.1
Coyhaique aerodrome	310	-45.5939 ^o	-72.1086 ^o	1205.9
Balmaceda aerodrome	520	-45.9125 ^o	-71.6933 ^o	611.6
Chile Chico aerodrome	328	-46.9086 ^o	-71.6931 ^o	305.5
Lord Cochrane aerodrome	196	-47.2444 ^o	-72.5861 ^o	738.2
Punta Arenas airport	39	-53.0050 ^o	-70.8439 ^o	375.7
Puerto Williams aerodrome	30	-54.9317 ^o	-67.6156 ^o	467.3

Table 2.

Example of ten daily reports for wind velocity and direction (*data: Jan. 2011, Santiago-Quinta Normal*).

Day i	Frequency $F^{(1)}$ and Intensity $I^{(2)}$ distribution														Total records								
	N		NE		E		SE		S		SW		W			NW		VRB		Calm			
	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I	F	I		F	I	F	I	F	I		
01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	4	1	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	0	8
02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	3	4	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	8
03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	5	4	4	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	8
04	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	5	5	1	5	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8
05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	3	4	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0	8
06	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	0	8
07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	3	3	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8
08	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	3	2	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	0	8
09	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	3	2	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	0	8
10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	4	4	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8

$F^{(1)}$: Number of records; $I^{(2)}$: Average wind velocity (knots).

Table 3.

Scalar characterisation of WDR and DRWP exposure for 29 Chilean cities (*data: November 2002- October 2012*).

WEATHER STATION	daDRI (m ² /s)	maDRI (m ² /s)	aaDRI (m ² /s)	DRWP _A (Pa)	RIWP (-)
Arica airport	0.0014	0.0016	0.0018	3.2075	0.08
Iquique airport	0.0002	0.0003	0.0003	6.0734	0.16
Calama aerodrome	0.0230	0.0275	0.0285	26.8083	0.77
Antofagasta (<i>Cerro Moreno airport</i>)	0.0067	0.0067	0.0069	6.2123	0.17
Atacama desert airport	0.0420	0.0350	0.0363	9.7356	0.27
La Serena (<i>La Florida aerodrome</i>)	0.1825	0.1677	0.1860	2.9696	0.07
Valparaiso aerodrome	2.2488	1.4838	1.6986	8.6166	0.36
Santo Domingo aerodrome	1.2393	0.9890	1.2023	4.3292	0.19
Santiago (<i>Quinta Normal</i>)	0.2184	0.1893	0.2973	0.5740	0.03
Tobalaba aerodrome	0.3645	0.2910	0.4055	0.9384	0.05
Pudahuel Santiago	0.5045	0.3917	0.5222	3.6724	0.11
Juan Fernández	3.4945	3.3655	3.5096	14.5449	0.59
Curico aerodrome	1.9576	1.3544	1.5394	0.8910	0.24
Chillán aerodrome	3.9686	2.5771	2.4561	3.6718	0.49
Concepción (<i>Carriel Sur airport</i>)	5.1037	3.2755	3.2457	11.4504	0.70
Los Ángeles aerodrome	4.0993	3.0139	3.2552	11.4127	0.59
Temuco (<i>Maqueue aerodrome</i>)	3.2119	2.3983	2.3505	4.3155	0.41
Valdivia aerodrome	8.2073	5.3865	5.3001	10.6756	1.04
Osorno aerodrome	4.3794	3.4571	3.5173	7.8475	0.57
Puerto Montt (<i>El Tepual airport</i>)	6.2741	4.5984	4.3988	7.6171	0.79
Futaleufu aerodrome	2.9399	3.4576	3.6516	5.6772	0.39
Alto Palena aerodrome	2.1613	2.7994	2.9798	5.2674	0.30
Puerto Aysén aerodrome	1.9285	2.2245	1.8511	4.5294	0.26
Coyhaique aerodrome	2.9476	2.6946	2.8220	5.3725	0.39
Balmaceda aerodrome	3.3785	3.4897	3.8041	34.6703	1.08
Chile Chico aerodrome	0.6578	0.8789	1.0583	17.9298	0.52
Lord Cochrane aerodrome	1.1098	1.3775	1.4653	5.1490	0.19
Punta Arenas airport	2.5018	2.5277	2.5505	29.6148	0.90
Puerto Williams aerodrome	1.6242	1.4436	1.3568	23.3785	0.70

Table 4.

Comparison of the scalar indices and maximum directional values for the WDR and DRWP exposures.

WEATHER STATION	$daDRI$ (m^2/s)	$max. daDRI_{\theta}$ (m^2/s)	$DRWP_A$ (Pa)	$max. DRWP_{A\theta}$ (Pa)
Antofagasta	0.0067	0.0041 (180°)	6.2123	6.3231 (180°)
La Serena	0.1825	0.0850 (105°)	2.9696	3.4532 (270°)
Santiago	0.2184	0.1275 (195°)	0.5740	1.1680 (180°)
Concepción	5.1037	4.3290 (0°)	11.4504	13.7345 (0°)
Temuco	3.2119	2.0893 (15°)	4.3155	4.0049 (270°)
Puerto Montt	6.2741	5.3088 (0°)	7.6171	9.4865 (0°)

Figure captions

Fig. 1. Cosine projection method for the semi-empirical calculation of wind-driven rain over a particular façade with an orientation θ [36].

Fig. 2. Location of the weather stations used in this study and the most relevant geographic/atmospheric factors that impact the Chilean climate.

Fig. 3. WDR exposure map of Chile.

Fig. 4. DRWP exposure map of Chile.

Fig. 5. Classification of locations with greater risk of water penetration in Chile. *Only sites with radii (i.e. RIWP values) that are at risk of water penetration greater than 0.4 were named.*

Fig. 6. Best fit-linear relationship between $daDRI$ and $maDRI$.

Fig. 7. Best fit-linear relationship between $daDRI$ and $aaDRI$.

Fig. 8. Best fit-linear relationship between $maDRI$ and $aaDRI$, and a comparison between different countries.

Fig. 9. Best fit-linear relationship between $DRWP_A$ and *mean wind pressure*.

Fig. 10. Directional component of the $daDRI$ value for the 8 main geographical directions (m^2/s) in six major cities in Chile.

Fig. 11. Directional $daDRI$ values (m^2/s) for 6 major cities in Chile (*angles are measured in degrees from the north*).

Fig. 12. Directional $DRWP_A$ values (Pa) for 6 major cities in Chile (*angles are measured in degrees from the north*).

Fig. 13. Best fit-linear relationships between scalar and maximum directional values for the WDR and DRWP exposures.

Figure 1

Fig. 1. Cosine projection method for the semi-empirical calculation of wind-driven rain over a particular façade with an orientation θ [36].

Figure 2

Fig. 2. Location of the weather stations used in this study and the most relevant geographic/atmospheric factors that impact the Chilean climate.

Figure 3

Fig. 3. WDR exposure map of Chile.

Figure 4

Fig. 4. DRWP exposure map of Chile.

Figure 5

Fig. 5. Classification of the locations with greater risk of water penetration in Chile. Only sites with radii (i.e. RIWP values) that are at risk of water penetration greater than 0.4 are named.

Figure 6

Fig. 6. Best fit-linear relationship between *daDRI* and *maDRI*.

Figure 7

Fig. 7. Best fit-linear relationship between *daDRI* and *aaDRI*.

Figure 8

Fig. 8. Best fit-linear relationship between *maDRI* and *aaDRI*, and a comparison between different countries.

Figure 9

Fig. 9. Best fit-linear relationship between $DRWP_A$ and mean wind pressure.

Antofagasta (Cerro Moreno airport)

La Serena (La Florida aerodrome)

Santiago (Quinta Normal)

Concepción (Carriel Sur airport)

Temuco (Maqueue aerodrome)

Puerto Montt (El Tepual airport)

Fig. 10. Directional component of the *daDRI* value for the 8 main geographical directions (m²/s) in six major cities in Chile.

Fig. 11. Directional *daDRI* values (m^2/s) for 6 major cities in Chile (angles are measured in degrees from north).

Fig. 12. Directional $DRWP_A$ values (Pa) for 6 major cities in Chile (angles are measured in degrees from north).

Figure 13

Fig. 13. Best fit-linear relationships between the scalar and maximum directional values for the WDR and DRWP exposures.